

THP-1 Protocol

Description:

- **Organism:** Homo sapiens, human
- **Tissue:** Peripheral blood
- **Morphology:** monocyte
- **Disease:** acute monocytic leukemia
- **Age:** 1 year
- **Gender:** male
- **BSL 1**
- **Growth properties:** suspension
- **Antigen expression:** HLA A2, A9, B5, DRw1, DRw2
- **Expression markers:** complement (C3) and Fc
- **Population doubling time:** approximately 26 hrs
- **Comments:** the cells are phagocytic (for both latex beads and sensitized erythrocytes) and lack surface and cytoplasmic immunoglobulin.

Complete medium:

- RPMI-1640 medium
- 10% FBS no heat-inactivated
- 1% L-glutamine
- 0.05 mM 2-mercaptoethanol

Reagents for cryopreservation:

Complete growth medium supplemented with 5% DMSO.

Thawing the cells:

1. Thaw the vial by gentle agitation in a 37°C water bath. Warning: to reduce the possibility of contamination, keep the O-ring and cap out of the water. Thawing should be rapid (approximately 2')
2. Remove the vial from the water bath as soon as the contents are thawed and decontaminate by dipping in or spraying with 70% ethanol. All the operations from this point on should be carried out under strict aseptic conditions
3. Transfer the vial contents to a centrifuge tube containing 9 mL complete culture medium and spin at 125 xg for 5-7'
4. Resuspend cell pellet with the recommended complete medium. Warning: it's important to avoid excessive alkalinity of the medium during recovery of the cells; it is suggested that, prior to the addition of the vials contents, the culture vessel containing the complete growth medium be placed into the incubator for at least 15 minutes to allow the medium to reach its normal pH (7.0 to 7.6).
5. Incubate the culture at 37°C in a suitable incubator. A 5% CO₂ in air atmosphere is recommended if using the medium described on this product sheet.

Subculturing procedure:

Growth properties: suspension

Cultures can be maintained by the addition of fresh medium or replacement of medium. Alternatively, cultures can be established by centrifugation with subsequent resuspension at 2-4x10⁵ viable cells/mL.

Subculture when cell concentration reached 8×10^5 cells/ml. Do not allow the cell concentration to exceed 1×10^6 cells/ml.

Interval: between 1×10^5 and 1.5×10^6 viable cells/ml

Medium Renewal: add fresh medium every 2 to 3 days

FAQs:

1. What culture conditions are preferred by THP-1 cells in order to maintain cell viability?

Recommended seeding density of 3×10^5 viable cells/ml. These suspension cells prefer conditioned medium and gentle handling instead of centrifugation and total medium replacement. Add cell culture media to dilute cells to maintenance densities.

Frequent cell counts are the best way to monitor. These cells should be fed by the simple addition of small amounts fresh medium to the flask (so that they have conditioned medium) every 2 to 3 days. You do not need to centrifuge the cells each time and re-seed. When cultured in our labs, by day 2 the cells are typically ready to be expanded to a larger flask with more medium. It is important to expand the culture when the cell density reaches 8×10^5 viable cells/ml. Do not allow the cell density to exceed 1×10^6 viable cells/ml.

2. How is complete medium prepared for THP-1?

To prepare a bottle of complete growth medium, add the following:

- 500 mL RPMI-1640 (ATCC 30-2001)
- 56 mL FBS (ATCC 30-2020) – not heat-inactivated

Note: Because of limited stability, the following components should be added to an aliquot of the above culture medium fresh prior to seeding or performing fluid additions. Do not store media supplemented with 2-Mercaptoethanol.

- Gibco 2-Mercaptoethanol (Catalog #21985-023): use $0.9 \mu\text{L}/1 \text{ mL}$ culture medium.

The FBS should not be heat-inactivated. If growth is slow, try using a different FBS and/or increasing the FBS concentration temporarily to 20%.